

Exploring Tools for Flaky Test Detection, Correction, and Mitigation: A Systematic Mapping Study

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Planning

Research Questions

RQ_1: What are the objectives of flaky test tools, and what techniques do they employ? This question seeks to clarify the specific functions of each collected tool, including the flaky testing contexts in which they operate and the techniques they utilize. Furthermore, it aims to compare tools with similar functionalities.

RQ_2: What are the main characteristics of flaky test tools, and which detection causes do they address? This RQ aims to compile a comprehensive list of all the tools and their key characteristics. Additionally, it aims to identify the causes of flaky tests targeted by each tool, providing researchers and professionals in the field with an overview of current tools to facilitate their selection process.

Search String

Title:("tool*" OR "detect*" OR "flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness") AND

Abstract:("flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "test code" OR "test flakiness" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool")

Sources

- ACM Digital Library (<http://portal.acm.org>)
- IEEE Digital Library (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>)
- Science@Direct (<http://www.sciencedirect.com>)
- Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com>)
- Springer Link (<http://link.springer.com>)

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- The summary mentions a flaky test detection tool
- The abstract mentions flaky test detection
- Propose, quote or use a flaky test detection tool

Exclusion Criteria:

- Websites, books, pamphlets and gray literature
- Full text not available online
- Work outside the scope of flaky test detection
- Papers with less than two pages
- Papers not in English

Conducting

Digital Libraries Search Strings

ACM Digital Library:

_____New (25/03/2023) - 49_____

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness"

AND

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool" OR "test code"

Title:("tool*" OR "detect*" OR "flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness")

AND

Abstract:("flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "test code" OR "test flakiness" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool")

IEEE Digital Library:

_____New (25/03/2023) - 45_____

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness"

AND

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool" OR "test code"

Title : tool* OR detect* OR flaky test OR flaky tests OR flakiness

AND

Abstract : flaky test OR flaky tests OR test flakiness OR flakiness

Science@Direct:

_____New (25/03/2023) - 03_____

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness"

AND

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool" OR "test code"

("flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "detect") AND ("flakiness")

Scopus:

_____New (08/04/2023) - 93_____

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness"

AND

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool" OR "test code"

("flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "detect") AND ("flakiness")

Springer Link:

_____New (25/03/2023) - 151_____

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness"

AND

"flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool" OR "test code"

("flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "flakiness") AND ("flaky test" OR "flaky tests" OR "test code"
OR "test flakiness" OR "flakiness" OR "test tool")

Imported Studies

- **ACM Digital Library:** 49
- **IEEE Digital Library:** 45
- **Science@Direct:** 3
- **Scopus:** 93
- **Springer Link:** 151